
CHIANTI

An Astrophysical Database for Emission Line Spectroscopy

CHIANTI TECHNICAL REPORT No. 34

The CHIANTI total ionization rate files (diparams, easplups)

1 Overview

This document describes the format for the CHIANTI diparams and easplups files, which contain the parameters used to compute the total ionization rate coefficient for an ion.

For CHIANTI, only ionization caused by collisions with free electrons is modeled. *Direct ionization* (DI) is when the colliding electron knocks a bound electron out of the ion. *Excitation–autoionization* (EA) is when the colliding electron excites the ion into an autoionizing state. This state can either decay to a bound state by releasing a photon, or it can autoionize. The latter case contributes to the ion’s ionization rate.

Ionization rates for all ions relevant to CHIANTI were assessed and published by Dere (2007). They were added to CHIANTI 6 (Dere et al., 2009), and updates for some ions were added to CHIANTI 10.1 (Dere et al., 2023).

The procedure for obtaining the ionization rates using the IDL software is given in Section 2. Details on how data for the DI rates are stored and processed are given in Section 3, and details for EA rates are given in Section 4.

2 Procedure

The ionization rates for the ion `ionname` (e.g., `o_5`) at a set of temperatures `temp` are obtained through the IDL call

```
IDL> rate=ioniz_rate(ionname,temp)
```

The returned quantity is the ionization rate coefficient in units of $\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$.

The optional inputs `di_rates=` and `ea_rates` can be specified to return the separate DI and EA rates.

3 Direct ionization

3.1 Assessment of the DI cross-sections

Direct ionization is usually considered in terms of ionizations of electrons from specific shells of the ion. Consider beryllium-like ions, for example, for which the ground state configuration is $1s^2 2s^2$. The incoming electron can remove either a $1s$ or a $2s$ electron. Therefore there are two DI “transitions” that combine to give the total DI rate. For a more complex ion, such as S-like Fe XI, ionization could potentially displace any of the $1s$, $2s$, $2p$, $3s$ or $3p$ electrons, but usually only the outer electron shells are important, and in fact the CHIANTI Fe XI DI file only contains the $3p$ cross-section.

The cross-sections for the transitions as a function of energy are usually calculated with an atomic physics code, with the Flexible Atomic Code (FAC: Gu, 2008) the most commonly used. If experimental cross-sections are available, then the theoretical cross-sections can be scaled to match the experimental values.

Dere (2007) performed FAC calculations for all ions of all elements up to zinc, and scaled the results to measurements where available. A novel feature of this work was to scale the energies and cross-sections using a method similar to Burgess & Tully (1992) and then perform spline fits such that the cross-sections could be defined for the entire energy range up to infinity. This then enabled the rate coefficient—the quantity needed for modeling astrophysical plasmas—to be calculated efficiently from the cross-section spline fits.

The spline fits are performed by the CHIANTI team data assessor using custom software, and the fits to the DI cross-sections are stored in the CHIANTI `diparams` file. For example, `fe_11.diparams` contains the fits for Fe XI.

3.2 The diparams file format

The format of the `diparams` is best illustrated through an example. We consider the `fe_11.diparams` file from CHIANTI 11:

```

26  11  11  1  3
2.00000  0.00000  0.03000  0.06200  0.12500  0.25000  0.37500  0.50000  etc.
290.24698  0.00000  1.20118  2.31960  4.09353  6.63702  8.84149  11.28847  etc.
1.300e+00  4.000e+00  2.000e+00
-1

```

(the second and third lines are truncated for display purposes).

The first line tells us the ion (26–Fe; 11–XI), the number of spline points (11), the number of ionization components (1), and the number of EA contributions (3). The fortran format for the numbers is `5i5`.

The second line contains the Burgess & Tully scaling factor (2.0), and then the eleven scaled energy points at which the spline fit is defined. The fortran format for the numbers is `f10.5`.

The third line contains the ionization energy (I) in eV, and then the scaled ionization cross-sections. The fortran format for the numbers is `f10.5`.

For Fe XI there is only one DI component, corresponding to ionization of an outer $3p$ electron from the ground configuration of $3s^23p^4$. For some ions there can be additional components due to ionization of inner shell electrons. For example, for Ne VII there is an additional component due to ionization of a $1s$ electron from the $1s^22s^2$ ground configuration. In this case there are two additional lines in the `diparams` files containing the data for this DI component (lines 4 and 5).

The fourth line of the `fe_11.diparams` file contains three scaling parameters related to excitation-autoionization, and are discussed further in Section 4.1. The fortran format for the numbers is `e12.3`.

The fifth line contains a `-1` denoting the end of the DI data. All further lines in the file below this are considered to be comments.

3.3 The cross-section

The `diparams` contains scaled energy (x) and cross-section (y) values, which are related to the incident electron energy (E) and cross-section (σ) by

$$x = 1 - \frac{\ln f}{\ln(E/I - 1 + f)} \quad (1)$$

$$y = \frac{E\sigma I}{\ln(E/I) + 1} \quad (2)$$

where I is the ionization energy, and f is a scaling parameter. The latter is chosen by the data assessor in order to best fit a spline through the cross-section energies, but is usually close to two.

In the CHIANTI IDL software, the routines `scale_bt` and `descale_bt` scale and descale, respectively, the energies and cross-sections. The manner of calling these routines is not straightforward and is illustrated by using the code from the `ioniz_rate` routine.

The `ioniz_rate` routine needs to compute the rate coefficient(s) for the temperature(s) specified by the user. For a single temperature, the routine considers the set of energies $I + x_i kT$, where x_i are the 12 Laguerre polynomial roots (Section 3.4). In the `ioniz_rate` code these energies are written as `egl`. They are converted to scaled energies with the call:

```
scale_bt,egl,dum,dum,btf(ifac),ev1(ifac),btgl,dum,dum
```

`dum` is a dummy variable that is not used, `btf` is the scaling factor, f , `ev1` is the ionization energy, I , and the output is `btgl` which is the set of scaled energies.

The `ioniz_rate` code then uses the spline points in the `diparams` file to determine the scaled cross-sections that correspond to the scaled energies (`btgl`). The scaled cross-sections are named `btcross`. These are then converted back to cross-sections with a call to `descale_bt`:

```
descale_bt,btgl,btcross,dum,btf(ifac),ev1(ifac),evd2,crossgl,odum
```

where `evd2` and `crossgl` are the descaled energies and cross-sections, respectively. The former is identical to `egl`.

3.4 The rate coefficient

The `diparams` file contains spline fits to DI cross-sections (not rate coefficients). The rate coefficient, $q(T)$ is recovered from the cross-section by performing a Gauss-Laguerre integration. It is given by

$$q(T) = \int_0^\infty v f(E) \sigma(E) dE \quad (3)$$

where f is the Maxwellian distribution function, σ is the cross-section, E is the energy of the incoming electron, and v is the electron velocity ($E = m_e v^2/2$, where m_e is the electron mass). This can be written as

$$q(T) = 2 \left(\frac{2}{\pi m_e} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{1}{kT} \right)^{3/2} \int_0^\infty E \sigma(E) \exp\left(-\frac{E}{kT}\right) dE. \quad (4)$$

For direct ionization, $\sigma = 0$ for $E \leq I$, where I is the ionization potential. We can thus set $E' = E - I$ and rewrite Equation 4 as

$$q(T) = 2 \left(\frac{2}{\pi m_e} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{1}{kT} \right)^{3/2} \exp \left(-\frac{I}{kT} \right) \int_0^\infty (E' + I) \sigma(E') \exp \left(-\frac{E'}{kT} \right) dE'. \quad (5)$$

We now set $x = E'/kT$ and $x_0 = I/kT$, giving

$$q(T) = 2 \left(\frac{2}{\pi m_e} \right)^{1/2} (kT)^{1/2} \exp(-x_0) \int_0^\infty (x + x_0) \sigma(x) \exp(-x) dx. \quad (6)$$

The constant evaluates to $5.287 \times 10^{13} \text{ g}^{-1/2}$. The integral is now in a form where it can be accurately evaluated using Gauss-Laguerre integration. For CHIANTI we use a 12th-order Laguerre polynomial, giving

$$q(T) = 5.287 \times 10^{13} (kT)^{1/2} \exp(-x_0) \sum_{i=1}^{12} [w_i x_i \sigma(x_i) + w_i x_0 \sigma(x_i)] \quad \text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where the x_i and w_i are the roots and weights of the polynomial, which can be obtained from mathematical tables or an online search. The coefficients are also hard-coded into the `ioniz_rate` routine.

Equation 7 is evaluated within the routine `ioniz_rate`, where the numerical constant is written as `alpha`, $(kT)^{1/2}$ is written as `beta`, x_0 is written as `x0`, the w_i are written as `wgl`, the x_i are written as `xgl`, and the $\sigma(x_i)$ are written as `crossgl`. The code is:

```
newcross=alpha*beta*exp(-x0)*(total(wgl*xgl*crossgl)+x0*total(wgl*crossgl))
```

Although the output is called `newcross` it is actually the rate coefficient. In Section 3.3 it was shown that `crossgl` is the descaled cross-section as a function of the incident electron energy, which is written in the software as `egl`. In the above code, the outgoing electron energy `xgl` is used for evaluating the integral, consistent with Equation 7.

4 Excitation-autoionization

Electron excitation is one of the two core atomic processes (the other is radiative decay) at the heart of CHIANTI. The data are stored in `scups` files (CHIANTI Technical Report No. 13) which contain scaled effective collision strengths (or “upsilons”). Prior to CHIANTI 8, the collision strengths were stored in `splups` files that are in a different format. Specifically the `splups` files could store a maximum of only 9 spline points, whereas the `scups` files can store an unlimited number of spline points.

The EA rate is simply an electron excitation rate multiplied by a fraction that is the ratio of the autoionization rate of the excited rate to the combined autoionization rate and radiative stabilization rate (this is a fixed number). We can therefore use the same method for storing the EA rates as for the electron excitation rates. As the EA rates were introduced prior to CHIANTI 8, they are stored in the old `splups` format and the file extension is `easplups`. Thus the Fe XI EA data are stored in `fe_11.easplups`.

To demonstrate the difference between DI and EA rates, consider the case of Ne VII which has the $1s^2 2s^2$ ground configuration. Direct ionization can eject either a $1s$ or a $2s$ electron. Excitation of a $2s$ electron will always be to a bound state of the ion (i.e., the energy is below the ionization energy), and so this does contribute to the EA rate. However, a $1s$ electron can be excited to a higher shell such that the excited state has an energy above the ionization energy. For example, the final state can be $1s 2s^2 2p$ or $1s 2s^2 3p$. Autoionization of these states leads to a contribution to the EA rate.

As with the DI rates, EA rates are computed using atomic codes, with FAC being widely used. Cross-sections for excitations are computed for a set of incoming electron energies. The cross-sections are then bundled according to principal quantum number. Thus, for the Ne VII example, the rates for $1s^2 2s^2 - 1s 2s^2 2p$ are bundled, and the rates for $1s^2 2s^2 - 1s 2s^2 3l$ ($l = s, p, d$) are bundled. Cross-sections for each bundle are stored in the CHIANTI file `easplom` as scaled collision strengths (“omegas”). These files are then processed by custom CHIANTI software to yield the `easplups` files. The `easplom` files are not used by the CHIANTI modeling software.

An important point to note is that the `easplups` data file is linked to the `diparams` file. If the fifth column of line 1 in the `diparams` file (Section 3) is zero, then the `easplups` will not be read, even if it exists. In addition, the last data line of the `diparams` contains coefficients for scaling the EA rates (see below).

4.1 The easplups file format

The `easplups` file contains one or more lines of data and each line has the same format, which is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Data format for the `easplups` files.

Column	Format	Parameter
1	i3	Atomic number
2	i3	Spectroscopic number (e.g., 13 for “XIII”)
3	i3	Index for initial state
4	i3	Index for final state
5	i3	Transition type (either 1 or 4)
6	e10.3	Weighted oscillator strength (gf)
7	e10.3	Transition energy in eV units
8-8+n	e10.3	Spline values

Columns 3 and 4 give the indices of the initial and final states for the excitation part of the process. These are not the level indices found in the CHIANTI `elvlc` file, but instead refer to level bundles. The bundles are not identified in the `easplups` file, nor in any other CHIANTI file, and the reader is referred to Dere (2007) for more details.

The file is read directly using the routine `read_splups`. For example,

```
IDL> read_splups, 'fe_11.easplups', ea_splups
```

where the output `splups` is a structure

4.2 The rate coefficient

The EA rate coefficient is computed within the routine `ioniz_rate` and added to the DI rate coefficient to yield the total ionization rate coefficient. To compute it, the spline fit to the scaled EA effective collision strengths first has to be converted to effective collision strengths with the routine `descale_all`. For example:

```
descale_all, temperature, ea_splups, iups, ups
```

where `temperature` is an array of temperatures for which the collision strengths are required, `iups` is an index specifying which transition is needed, and `ups` is the output collision strength.

The effective collision strength is converted to the EA rate coefficient through the expression

$$q_{\text{EA}}(T) = 8.63 \times 10^{-6} f_{\text{EA}} \Upsilon(T) \exp\left(-\frac{E}{kT}\right) \frac{1}{T^{1/2}} \quad (8)$$

where f_{EA} is a scaling parameter, Υ is the effective collision strength (`ups`), and E is the energy for the transition (from the `easplups` file). The parameter f_{EA} is from the `diparams` file. In the Fe XI example (Section 3.2), the values 1.3, 4.0 and 2.0 are the f_{EA} values that are applied to the collision strengths on the 1st, 2nd and 3rd lines of the `easplups` file, respectively.

References

- Burgess, A., & Tully, J. A. 1992, *A&A*, 254, 436
- Dere, K. P. 2007, *A&A*, 466, 771, doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20066728
- Dere, K. P., Del Zanna, G., Young, P. R., & Landi, E. 2023, *ApJS*, 268, 52, doi: 10.3847/1538-4365/acec79
- Dere, K. P., Landi, E., Young, P. R., et al. 2009, *A&A*, 498, 915, doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/200911712
- Gu, M. F. 2008, *Canadian Journal of Physics*, 86, 675, doi: 10.1139/p07-197

A Document history

Version 1.1, 21-Jul-2025. Changed f to f_{EA} in Section 4.2 to differentiate it from f in Section 3.3.

Version 1.0, 18-Apr-2025.